

The Impact of Money Supply on Inflation in Nigeria (1981 - 2021)

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Suggested Citation

Okeke, C.C. (2023). The Impact of Money Supply on Inflation in Nigeria (1981 - 2021). *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(5), 236-253.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).16](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).16)

Abstract:

This study examined the impact of money supply on inflation in Nigeria between 1981 and 2021, using Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach is employed to estimate long run relationship amongst variables. The data for the variables were sourced from CBN statistical Bulletin 2021 edition. The results of the test established a significant long run positive and negative relationship between Inflation and Interest towards money supply on inflation *in Nigeria*. Based on the results of the variables, it is therefore

recommended that the policies put in place by the monetary and fiscal authorities in Nigeria should be such that will encourage the supply of money to a certain level in order to curb inflation in Nigeria in the short medium and long term.

Keywords: *Inflation, Money Supply, Interest, ARDL, Nigeria.*

Introduction

The maintenance of price stability is one of the main objectives of Macroeconomic Management (CBN, 1998). In order to achieve this, the monetary authority needs to control the amount of money in circulation through the use of monetary instrument such as bank lending rate, reserve requirement and so on, monetary policy has been defined as an action of the monetary authority to influence the quantity, cost and availability of money credit in order to achieve desired macroeconomic objectives of internal and external balances (CBN, 2011). While inflation on the other hand, has been described as persistence and appreciable increase in general price level of goods and services over a period of time (Jhingan, 2002). However, it is not in every case that an increase in price level of goods and services could be referred to as inflation. Thus, for an increase in general price level is regarded as inflation. Therefore, for an increase in price level to be regarded as inflation,

such an increase must be constant, enduring and sustainable. For inflation to occur therefore, the price level should affect almost every commodity and should not be temporal. Hence, since the money supply also affects price levels, monetary stability can help maintain price stability (Ryczkowski, 2021).

More so, the rising trend in the inflation rate in Nigeria has become a source of concern to the government, policy makers, researchers, and members of the public. According to Okere and Sanni (2005); Nwachukwu, Philip, Dibia, Azukaego Christopher, Ogudo and Pius (2014) inflation has become one of the perennial problems that have plagued the nation especially in the late 1980s and 1990s. Particularly in the year 2020, Nigeria experienced double-digit inflation and it has become a major threat to economic activities, especially on workers whose standard of living declines continuously (Okotori, 2020).

Moreover, inflation in the Nigerian economy is generally thought of as a complex phenomenon, which however tends to be greatly grown as a result of several factors. The recorded increase of inflation rate in the Nigerian economy shows clearly the failure of the existing economy policies in maintaining the stability of the general level of prices. Notwithstanding this fact, the average rate of inflation rate in Nigeria reached 22.79% during 2006 – 2023, and would move beyond that, which reflected the speed of product price change explaining the general rise in commodity and service prices. To sum up, it has been confirmed that there is a major effect of economic inflation rate on the Nigerian economy. The aim of the present research is to investigate the relationship between money supply and inflation in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are: to ascertain the impact of Money Supply on inflation in Nigeria, to determine how Gross Domestic Product relates to inflation in Nigeria, to ascertain the relationship between Import and inflation in Nigeria, to determine how the Exchange Rate is related to inflation in Nigeria, to ascertain the Interest Rate relates to inflation in Nigeria, to determine the relationship between Budget Deficit and inflation in Nigeria, to ascertain how Domestic Debt relates to inflation in Nigeria and to ascertain Total Government Debt relates to inflation in Nigeria. This study intends to answer the following questions: Does Money Supply ascertain the impact of Money Supply on inflation in Nigeria? Does Gross Domestic Product relates to inflation in Nigeria? What is the relationship between Import and inflation in Nigeria? Does Exchange Rate relates to inflation in Nigeria? Does Interest Rate relates to inflation in Nigeria? What is the relationship between Budget Deficit and inflation in Nigeria? Does Domestic Debt relates to inflation in Nigeria? Does Total Government Debt relates to inflation in Nigeria? The following hypotheses which are stated in the null form are tested in this study:

H₀₁: Money supply has no impact on inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Gross Domestic Product does not have a relationship with inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Import does not have a relationship with inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₄: Exchange Rate is not related to inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₅: Interest Rate is not related to inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₆: Budget Deficit has no relationship with inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₇: Domestic Debt is not related to inflation in Nigeria.

H₀₈: Total Government Debt is not related to inflation in Nigeria.

Money supply is one of the key factors of inflation, and many industrialized and emerging countries have faced and continue to face the enormous challenge of inflation throughout history. Higher inflation has severe negative impacts and must be kept within its limits. As a result, it should be investigated for policy development and implications in order to maintain it within bounds. Because of the positive influence on various income earning groups, creeping inflation is acceptable in the speed of economic expansion. Some economists feel that a low and constant inflation rate of 3% carries a minor economic cost (Mankiw, 2011). According to available empirical evidence, Nigeria has experienced low inflation. The rest of the paper is structured around four sections; the next section two contains the literature review, section three presents the data and methods, and section four includes the results and discussion.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature

Theoretical literature on the impact of Money supply on inflation in Nigeria is filled with contradictory views with regard to the causes of inflation. In fact, there are several theories that explain what causes inflation; however, most of them are formulated on the basis of the aggregate demand (demand – pull) and cost-push theories. Even though there are some controversies surrounding these two theories

(Ball and Doyle, 1969, as cited in Greenidge & DaCosta, 2009), amongst all the arguments, they are the least controversial and lay the foundation for debates on inflation. Below are the theoretical explanations as postulated by various economists and schools of thought.

(A) Demand-Pull or Monetary Theories of Inflation

Demand-pull or monetary theories of inflation define inflation situations where aggregate demand for goods and services exceeds aggregate supply, thereby leading to a general rise in price levels (Otto & Ukpere, 2016). This approach states that high government spending policies of central banks to raise money supply, rise in household and firms' consumption and prices in the international market compared to that of the domestic market are responsible for raising the price level (Ogbokor & Sunde 2011). The demand-pull paradigm is of the view that inflation exists when aggregate demand for goods and services exceeds aggregate supply for goods and services, such that the excess aggregate demand cannot be satisfied by running down the existing stocks, diverting suppliers from the export market to the domestic market, increasing imports or postponed demand (Anyanwu, 1993).

The demand-pull inflation may also be called surplus demand inflation because it arises from too much money chasing too few goods. Anyanwu (1993) opined that this was the situation during the Biafra-Nigeria war and after the Udoji Salary Awards of 1974 when wages increased astronomically. Higher wages increased the purchasing power of consumers thus leading to increased demand. The pressure on commodities, therefore, led to increases in their prices. More often it occurs where there is full employment so that the excess pressure on the factors of production leads to higher prices for the factors, ultimately leading to a rise in the cost of production. It could also be a short-run phenomenon where demand dynamics were not well anticipated. When there are production constraints, demand beyond the possible output level could also create inflation.

(B) Cost-Push Theories of Inflation

Cost-push inflation exists when wages or production costs start rising. The producers in turn pass these rising costs upon the consumers, leading to higher prices (Undji & Kaulihowa, 2015). Depreciation of the exchange rate can initiate an increase in the prices of goods as most firms import the bulk of raw materials required for their production at higher prices. Ogbokor & Sunde (2011) noted that this kind of inflation occurs mainly because of a rise in the cost of imported raw materials and an increase in the cost of labour. Otto & Ukpere (2016) noted that cost-push inflation can also be called "market power inflation" because the increase in the prices of goods and services originates from the supply side of the economy. These increases may arise from increased wage rates or a fall in productivity which also increases the cost of labour output. It may also arise out of other factors of production or cost of inputs such as power supply, transport or raw materials. In Nigeria, multiple taxation and corruption are major suspects. Alexander, Andow & Danpome (2015) opined that the cost-push theory maintains that prices of goods and services rise because wages are pushed up by trade unions' bargaining power, or by the pricing policies of oligopolistic and monopolistic firms with market power. The cost-push view attributed inflation to a host of non-monetary supply-oriented influences of shocks that raise costs and consequently prices. Onwiodukit (2002) noted that this school of thought attributes inflation to random non-monetary shocks such as crop failures, commodity shortages, vagaries of weather and an increase in the price of oil.

(C) The Classical Theory of Inflation

The classical theory of inflation is derived directly from the classical quantity theory of money which is one of the oldest surviving economic doctrines. The theory is found in the famous equation of exchange developed in the 19th century by Irving Fisher (1876 – 1947). Fisher's equation of exchange states that $MV = PY$. If velocity (V) and output (Y) are constant, the increase in money (M) will cause a direct and proportionate increase in prices (P) (Almahdi &

Faroug, 2018). The theory assumes full employment in the economy while M is exogenously determined by the monetary authority. The greatest shortcoming of this theory is that it does not explain the channel (whether interest rate, wages, unemployment, demand, etc.) by which an increase in money supply causes the rise in the price level.

Empirical Literature Review

Several studies have examined the impact of money on inflation in both developed and developing nations although only a few of them are done in Nigeria. However, the impact of money supply on macroeconomic variable performance such as inflation has gained considerable pronouncement in Literature, where many developing countries including Nigeria are making financial efforts to ensure price stability in order to promote economic growth. Empirically, Oumbe (2018) examined the “effect of monetary policy on inflation” and the “nature of the relationship between money supply and inflation in Cameroon”. Time series annual data was used from 1980 to 2016. Johansen's Co-integration test was used to determine the relationship between money supply and inflation. Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation technique was used to examine the effect of money supply and inflation in Cameroon. Toda and Yamamoto's causality tests were also used to test the causality between money supply and inflation. The result showed that there is a long-run equilibrium relationship between money supply and inflation; money supply had a significant and positive impact on inflation in Cameroon and there is one-way causality from money supply to inflation. The study also exhibited that inflation has a monetary source in Cameroon. Thus, monetary policy should be planned to maintain the stability of price by controlling the growth of the money supply in the economy of Cameroon.

Olorunfemi & Adeleke (2013) also examined the effect of money supply on inflation by including interest rate as one of the control variables, using monthly data from 1980 to 2010. The study utilized the OLS method and concluded that money supply and interest rate did influence

inflation in Nigeria. Tang and Lean (2007) found that the effect of money supply ($M1$) on inflation in Malaysia is negative and statistically significant at a 1 percent level. Roffia and Zaghini (2008) analyzed the data of 15 industrialized countries and found that there is no positive correlation between money growth rate and price index in at least 50% of the cases.

Kiganda (2014) tested the relationship between inflation and money supply in Kenya through the use of annual time series data during the period of 1984–2012. The results indicated that there is a significant positive long-run relationship between inflation and money supply, and inflation is significantly error correcting at 68% annually. Islam, Ghani, Mahyudin & Manickam (2017) investigated the determinants of factors that affect inflation in Malaysia, variables used are money supply, exchange rate, and inflation, the quantitative method of analysis was adopted. The result indicates that a rise in the unemployment rate will lead the inflation rate to decrease to a drop and vice versa. The relationship between exchange rate and inflation is negative, whereas money supply and inflation have a positive relationship.

Ofori-Frimpon et al. (2017) studied the effect of money supply on inflation rate in Ghana using annual data from 1967 to 2015 to test the model. The research was restricted to using money supply as an independent variable on the dependent variable, which was an inflation rate. The results showed that there was a long-run positive link between money supply and inflation rate based on an Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method.

Obi & Uzodigwe (2015) supported the argument by monetarists who argue that inflation is essentially a monetary phenomenon in the sense that a continuous rise in the general price level is due to the rate of expansion in money supply far in excess of the money actually demanded by economic units. The study assessed the dynamic linkage between money supply and inflation in ECOWAS member states; West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ) and West African Economic Monetary Union (WAEMU) from

the period 1980 to 2012. They used both the univariate and panel data, to assess the stationary properties of the series. The random effect model for ECOWAS member states shows that the impact of money supply on inflation is effective in the current and first period. While the impact is effective in the first period for WAMZ, WAEMU experiences the impact in current period. They also found significant specific-country effects on the variables.

AlNaif et al. (2018) analyzed the relationship between the money supply and inflation during the period of 1968–2015 in Jordan. They used a methodology of econometric analysis of time series. The results indicated that “there was no causal link between the money supply and the price index in the long term, and money supply causes inflation not vice versa in the short term in Jordan.”

Sultana et al. (2019) checked the “relationship between money supply and inflation in Bangladesh” using monthly data from May 2010 to December 2017, the Co-Integration, and Vector Error Correction Techniques. They demonstrated that the money supply did not affect inflation in the short term, not vice versa. They also found a bidirectional causal relationship between money supply and inflation in the long term.

Danlami et al. (2020) investigated money supply and inflation using the ARDL technique. It was found that economic variables are not integrated in the same order. The money supply increment was found to demonstrate inflationary pressure in the short run. However, in the long run, the money supply was found to have no significant influence on inflation.

Hicham (2020) said that Money supply, Economic Growth and inflation rate has the period of 1970–2018 in Algeria using Co-Integration and Causality Analysis. The findings lend credence to the monetarist theory of inflation rate on the grounds that an increase in the money supply has no effect on the rate of economic growth.

Gap in literature

The main motivation of this study is to assess the effect of money supply on inflation in Nigeria. There are ample empirical evidence in the literature about money supply and inflation some of them are Sultana (2019), Oumbe (2018), Islam, Ghani, Mahyudin and Manickan (2017), Ofori, Danqua and Zhang(2017), AlNaif, Shahtite, & AlTaib, (2018), Obi and Uzodigwe (2015), Olorunfemi & Adeleke (2013) and Kiganda (2014). However, all these studies reviewed above and the results obtained have their theoretical backing in the monetarist view. Also it will be noted that there are some literatures which have contrary opinion from the monetarist view. They believe that inflation is not only a monetary phenomenon as there are other factors that affect inflation in an economy. Some of these studies are Tang and Lean (2007), Roffia and Zaghini (2008), Hicham (2020) and Danlami, Abdulhamid, Hidthiir, and Sallahuddin (2020) and so on. Hence this study makes an attempt at filling the gap in the literature and presents an analysis of the effect of money supply on inflation in Nigeria by combining gross domestic product among other variables to examine how money supply affects inflation in the economy.

Methodology

Annual Time Series Data covering the period of 1981 to 2021 which were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin 2021 Edition was used in this study. Using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), the variables are subjected to stationary testing. Time series characteristics of the research variables need to be studied in order to determine the order of their integration. Time series data are mostly not stationary, meaning that the mean, variance, and covariance of such data sets are not invariant in time (Gujarati, 2009). Non-stationary series can result in spurious and misleading regression. This study employs descriptive statistics and the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology which suggested by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) for the analysis of data.

Theoretical Framework

To illustrate the impact of Money supply on inflation in Nigeria, it takes into account the guidance on the methodology of Hicham (2020) with some modifications to the variables and technology employed to fit the data and the case study of Nigeria. Using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test was conducted and the result necessitated the test for the short-run and long-run relationship among the variables (co-integration). Also, the study employs the Auto- Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology suggested by Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001) for the analysis of data.

Model specification

The model which hypothesised variations in inflation to be a function of the explanatory variables are algebraically specified. The Model is specified based on demand-pull theories.

Model

The model is thus:

$$INF = f(MS, GDP, IMP, EXR, INT, BD, DD, TGD) \quad (1)$$

Where:

- MS* = MoneySupply (N' Billion)
- GDP* = GrossDomesticProduct
- IMP* = Import(N' Billion)
- EXR* = ExchangeRate
- INT* = InterestRate(%)
- BD* = BudgetDeficit(N' Billion)
- DD* = DomesticDebt(N' Billion)
- TGD* = TotalGovernmentDebt(N' Billion)
- INF* = Inflation(%)

The parameterized version of the inflation model is presented as:

$$INF = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MS_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 IMP_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 INT_t + \beta_6 BD_t + \beta_7 DD_t + \beta_8 TGD_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

In order to estimate equation, we specify it in econometric form as:

$$INF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MS_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 IMP_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 INT_t + \beta_6 BD_t + \beta_7 DD_t + \beta_8 TGD_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where:

$\beta_0 = \text{Intercept}$

β_i (where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8$) are parameters to be estimated

$\varepsilon_t = \text{error term}$

However, a log-linear form is more likely to find evidence of a deterrent effect than a linear form, we therefore log-linearized equation as:

$$\ln INF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MS_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 IMP_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 INT_t + \beta_6 BD_t + \beta_7 DD_t + \beta_8 TGD_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

$\ln = \text{natural log of their respective variables}$
(5)

Priori Expectation of the Model

The expected signs of the coefficients of the explanatory variables are:

$$\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 > 0, \beta_5 > 0, \beta_6 > 0, \beta_7 > 0, \beta_8 > 0.$$

INF_t is used as a measure of predictive variable.

Estimation Technique and Procedure

Descriptive statistics:

The descriptive coefficients compiling a data set that is either a representation of entire population or a sample is called Descriptive Statistics. The main purpose is to provide a summary of the samples and measures done on the study. However, it involves the use of graph to show the trends of all variables used in the research.

Test for Unit Root:

The presence of trends and unit roots are detected from the slowly decaying autocorrelation function in univariate process which indicates non-stationarity. Consider $AR(p)$ model so that

$$Y_t = \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t$$

Which can be written as

$$\psi(L)y_t = \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

where $\psi(L) = 1 - \phi_1 L - \phi_2 L^2 - \dots - \phi_p L^p$

is a polynomial in lag L.

If the root of the characteristic equation $\psi(L) = 0$ are all greater than unity in absolute term, then y_t is

stationary, otherwise y_t is non stationary.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test:

The ADF test belongs to a category of tests called ‘Unit Root Test’, which is the proper method for testing the stationary of a time series. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller test checks through these models:

$$\Delta y_t = (\rho - 1)y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1)y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \delta_t + (\rho - 1)y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (9)$$

Hypotheses Tests are specified as:

$H_0: \rho = 1$ vs $H_1: \rho < 1$

$H_0: \alpha = 0$ vs $H_1: \alpha \neq 0$

$H_0: \gamma = 0$ vs $H_1: \gamma \neq 0$

The test statistic is specified as:

$$T_\rho = \frac{\hat{\rho}}{S.E.(\hat{\rho})} \simeq ADF(I, n, \alpha)$$

Is compared with the appropriate value of Dickey Fuller table.

The null hypothesis for the tests is that the data are non-stationary, and it is rejected for this test so that we want a p-value of less than 0.05.

ARDL Bounds Test for Co integration:

In order to empirically analyze the long – run relationships and short run dynamic interactions among the variables of interest we apply the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) co integration technique the ARDL bounds test is

based on the assumption that the variables are I(0) and I(1) (pesaran etal, 2001).

Short Run and Long Run Estimation of the ARDL model:

The short run equation in our model is given as follows:

$$INF_{t-1} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 D(MS)_{t-1} + \beta_2 D(GDP)_{t-1} + \beta_3 D(IMP)_{t-1} + \beta_4 D(EXR)_{t-1} + \beta_5 D(INT)_{t-1} + \beta_6 D(BD)_{t-1} + \beta_7 D(DD)_{t-1} + \beta_8 D(TGD)_{t-1} + ECM(-1) \quad (10)$$

Where “D” represents the first difference operation of the variables, ECM (-1) is the one period lag of the model residual. The parameters β_1 to β_8 are the short run coefficients of the model while the coefficient of ECM (-1) is the long run speed of adjustment of the model. The sign of the coefficient of ECM (-1) should be negative and significant as well for holding the long run equilibrium (Dhungel, 2014).

The long run equation can be stated thus:

$$INF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MS_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 IMP_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 INT_t + \beta_6 BD_t + \beta_7 DD_t + \beta_8 TGD_t + \mu_t \quad (11)$$

Where the variables MS, GDP, IMP, EXR, INT, BD, DD and TGD are defined in equation 1

while the parameters β_1 to β_8 are the long run coefficients and “U” is the error term.

Granger causality test:

This study intends to use Granger causality test to ascertain the direction of causality between money supply and inflation in Nigeria. In Grangers causality relationship is expressed in two pairs of regression equations by simply twisting independent and dependent variables. Therefore, from the equation below the model specification on causality between money supply and inflation is specified as follows:

$$INF = \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_i INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_j MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_k GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_l IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_m EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_n INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_o BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_p DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \phi_q TGD_{t-1} \quad (12)$$

$$MS = \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_i MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_j GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_k IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_l EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_m INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_n BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_o DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_p TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \alpha_r INF_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t2} \quad (13)$$

$$GDP = \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_i GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_j IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_k EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_l INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_m BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_n DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_o TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_q INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \beta_r MS_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t3} \quad (14)$$

$$IMP = \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_i IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_j EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_k INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_l BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_m DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_n TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_o INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_p MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \lambda_r GDP_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t4} \quad (15)$$

$$EXR = \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_i EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_j INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_k BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_l DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_m TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_n INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_o MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_q GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \chi_r IMP_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t5} \quad (16)$$

$$INT = \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_i INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_j BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_k DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_l TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_m INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_n MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_o GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_p IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \delta_r EXR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t6} \quad (17)$$

$$BD = \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_i BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_j DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_k TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_l INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_m MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_n GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_o IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_q EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \varphi_r INT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t7} \quad (18)$$

$$DD = \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_i DD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_j TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_k INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_l MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_m GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_n IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_o EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_p INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \gamma_r BD_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t8} \quad (19)$$

$$TGD = \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_i TGD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_j INF_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_k MS_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_l GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_m IMP_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_n EXR_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_o INT_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_q BD_{t-1} + \sum_{t-i}^n \kappa_r DD_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{t9} \quad (20)$$

Results and Discussion

Preliminary Analysis

Trends in Inflation (1981-2021)

Inflation exhibits an upward moving slope. The graphical illustration in figure 4.1 shows the trend of Inflation in Nigeria from 1981 to 2021. Units are measured in percentages. Overall, the INF exhibits an upward slope and downward slope with the maximum value being 72.84000% in 2021 and a minimum value of 5.390000% in 1981. The weighted averages increased and decreased over the years as a result of inflation on the prices of commodities.

Trends in Money Supply (1981-2021)

The graph in figure 4.2 shows the line graph of money supply in Nigeria from 1981- 2021. During the period, the indicator reached a maximum value of N40318.29billion in 2021 and a minimum value of N14.47117billion in 1981. Over the period of forty years, money

supply in Nigeria maintained and upward trend showing that the total volume of money supply in the economy increased.

Figure 1. Trends in Inflation (1981-2021)

Figure 2. Trends in Money Supply (1981-2021)

Trends in Gross Domestic Product (1981-2021)

Figure 4.3 shows the trend of Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria for forty years. Overall, the Gross Domestic Product exhibits an upward slope. However, its value increased to a more than doubled valued in 2010 (from 139.3105 billion naira in 2009 to 176075.5 billion naira in 2010). This shows that production in the nation increased over the years showing economic growth, likewise increments in the prices at which goods and services are sold in the market.

Figure 3. Trends in GDP (1981-2021)

Trends in Import (1981-2021)

The graph in figure 4.4 shows the line graph of Import in Nigeria from 1981 - 2021. During the

period, the indicator reached a maximum value of N22394498 billion in 2021 and a minimum value of N5983.600 billion in 1981. Over the period of forty years, import in Nigeria maintained and upward and downward trend showing that the total volume of import in the economy increased.

Figure 4. Trends in Import (1981-2021)

Trends in Exchange Rate (1981 - 2021)

The graph in figure 4.5 shows the line graph of Exchange rate in Nigeria from 1981 - 2021. During the period, the indicator reached a maximum value of 399.9636 in 2021 and a minimum value of 0.610025 in 1981. Over the period of forty years, Exchange rate in Nigeria maintained and upward and downward trend showing that the total volume of Exchange rate in the economy increased.

Figure 5. Trends in Exchange Rate (1981 - 2021)

Trends in Interest (1981 - 2021)

The line graph in figure 4.6 illustrates the trends in interest rate in the country from 1981 to 2021. Units are measured in percentages (%). The interest rate is the most volatile of all the variables used in the study. It is characterized by high fluctuations in its movement over the period under consideration. During the period, the maximum value for interest rate was 23.99000% in 2021 while the lowest value was 4.704871% in 1981.

Figure 6. Trends in Interest (1981 - 2021)

Trends in Budget Deficit (1981-2021)

The figure 4.7 represents the trend of budget deficit during the period under study. The trend analysis between 1981 and 2021, budget deficit decreases negatively from N7118.708billion to N32.04940billion. Overall, there were negative fluctuations in its movement over the period under consideration.

Figure 7. Trends in Budget Deficit (1981-2021)

Trends in Domestic Debt (1981-2021)

The graph in figure 4.8 shows the line graph of Domestic Debt in Nigeria from 1981- 2021. During the period, the indicator reached a maximum value of N19242.56 billion in 2021 and a minimum value of N11.19260 billion in 1981. Over the period of forty years, Domestic Debt in Nigeria maintained and upward trend showing that the total volume of Domestic Debt in the economy increased.

Figure 8. Trends in Domestic Debt (1981-2021)

Trends in Total Government Debt (1981-2021)

The graph in figure 4.9 shows the line graph of Total Government Debt in Nigeria from 1981 - 2021. During the period, the indicator reached a maximum value of N35097.79 billion in 2021 and a minimum value of N13.52380 billion in 1981. Over the period of forty years, Total Government Debt in Nigeria maintained and upward and downward trend showing that the total volume of Total Government Debt in the economy increased.

Descriptive statistics show the qualities of the data we are using for estimation. This allows us to define the appropriate methodology for estimation. The table 1 (Appendix 1) summarizes the descriptive statistics.

Figure 9. Trends in Total Government Debt (1981-2021)

Table 1 (Appendix 1) presents the descriptive analysis of the time series properties of the variables included in the model. The descriptive statistics was carried out to report the essential properties of the variables. The table shows that Inflation, Money Supply, Gross Domestic Product, Import, Exchange Rate, Interest Rate, Budget Deficit, Domestic Debt and Total Government Debt are normally distributed given the probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistics of 0.000000, 0.001339, 0.002980, 0.000287, 0.038402, 0.020009, 0.000000, 0.000083 and 0.000000 respectively. Which all the variables are statistically significant, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis that the sample follows a normal distribution.

Table 2. Results of ADF Unit root test of Stationarity

Variables	ADF test statistic @ Levels	ADF test statistic @ First Difference	ADF test statistic @ Second Difference	Remark
LNINF	-2.993033	-6.557063		I (0)
LNMS	7.637631	1.295674		I (0)
LNGDP	12.54741	0.497483		I (0)
LNIMP	0.866108	0.607165	-6.625610	I (2)
LNEXR	2.714012	-4.074830	-5.973304	I (2)
LNINT	-2.376423	-5.487866	-10.46838	I (2)
LNBD	5.157590	3.372939		I (0)
LNDD	4.697343	3.115417		I (0)
LNTGD	4.000043	-0.335791		I (0)

Note: 5% Critical value: -2.936942 -2.94115

Source: The Author's Computation 2023.

The results of the ADF unit roots tests of the series in table 2 show that all the variables are stationary at levels except import, exchange rate and interest rate that are stationary at second difference. The variables are therefore integrated of order 0, 2 i.e. I (0) and I (2). The null hypothesis of unit root is therefore not accepted since the ADF test statistics are greater than the critical values at the indicated levels of significance. Thus, money supply on inflation in Nigeria as well as the modelled variables are stationary, which follows an integrating I (0) and I (2) processes. Having determined that ADF unit roots tests variables are integrated of order 0 and 2 and are stationary, the researcher moved on to verify whether the combination of the

variables are co – integrated and as such employed the ARDL bound test.

Table 3. Result of ARDL Bounds Test to Co – integration for the Model

Model	Result	
F – Statistic Value	= 5.344597	
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bounds	II Bounds
10%	1.85	2.85
5%	2.11	3.15
2.5%	2.33	3.42
1%	2.62	3.77

Source: The Author's Computation 2023.

From the results in table 3, the null hypotheses of no long – run relationships are rejected as the F – statistic value of 5.344597 is greater than the critical upper (II) bounds values of 3.15 at 5% level of significance for the model. This confirms the existence of long run relationships among the variables. Having established the

existence of long run relationships, short run and long run impact of the explanatory variables are estimated. The results of the short run and long run impact of the explanatory variables on inflation to Nigeria are presented in table 4 for the model.

Table 4. ARDL Short Run and Long Run Results for the Model (Dependent Variable: (INF))

Short – Run Result				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t - Statistic	Prob.
D(INF(-1))	0.598650**	0.142008	4.215600	0.0003
D(INF(-2))	-0.687265**	0.155657	-4.415245	0.0002
MSSNBN	0.004406	0.002946	1.495793	0.1467
GDPNBN	-0.000691	0.000830	-0.832801	0.4125
IMPBN	-8.53E-07	2.08E-06	-0.410421	0.6849
EXR	-0.138944	0.080024	-1.736292	0.0943
INT	-1.379344	0.719853	-1.916146	0.0664
D(INT(-1))	0.771388	0.688947	1.119662	0.2731
D(INT(-2))	2.372617**	0.620965	3.820855	0.0007
BUDGETDEFICITNBN	0.004375	0.006475	0.675589	0.5053
DOMESICDEBTNBN	-0.001381	0.006920	-0.199627	0.8433
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN	0.001775	0.001916	0.926192	0.3629
CointEq(-1)	-1.088615**	0.128342	-8.482128	0.0000
Long – Run Result				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t - Statistic	Prob.
MSSNBN	0.004047	0.002765	1.463955	0.1552
GDPNBN	-0.000635	0.000771	-0.823390	0.4178
IMPBN	-7.84E-07	1.90E-06	-0.411814	0.6839
EXR	-0.127634	0.069486	-1.836831	0.0777
INT	1.621016**	0.471221	3.440033	0.0020
BUDGETDEFICITNBN	0.004019	0.005934	0.677256	0.5042
DOMESICDEBTNBN	-0.001269	0.006363	-0.199414	0.8435
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN	0.001630	0.001748	0.932710	0.3596
C	7.772771	7.446061	1.043877	0.3062
R-squared	0.755656	Mean dependent var		19.08795
Adjusted R-squared	0.642881	S.D. dependent var		17.01370
S.E. of regression	10.16729	Akaike info criterion		7.737430
Sum squared resid	2687.717	Schwarz criterion		8.291950
Log likelihood	-137.8799	Hannan-Quinn criter.		7.936387
F-statistic	6.700598	Durbin-Watson stat		2.289459
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000026			

Source: The Author’s Computation 2023.

Note: ** denotes significant variables of the model.

The result in table 4, reveals that in the short run, the (INF (-1), (INF (-2) and (INTR (-2)) were significant but positive & negative impact on inflation to Nigeria. While, MSSNBN, GDPNBN, IMPNBN, EXR, INT, (INT (-1)), BUDGETDEFICITNBN,

DOMESICDEBTNBN & TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN were insignificant but positive & negative impact on inflation to Nigeria in the short run. Whereas, a unit increase in (INF(-1)), MSSNBN, (INT(-1)), (INT(-2)), BUDGETDEFICITNBN and

TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN increases inflation to Nigeria by 0.599%, 0.004%, 0.771%, 2.373%, 0.004% & 0.002%, respectively. While a unit increase in (INF(-2)), GDPNBN, IMPNBN, EXR, INT & DOMESICDEBTNBN lead to 0.687%, 0.007%, 0.000%, 0.139%, 1.379% & 0.001% decreases inflation to Nigeria. In the long run, INT was significant but positive impact on inflation to Nigeria. While MSSNBN, GDPNBN, IMPNBN, EXR, BUDGETDEFICITNBN, DOMESICDEBTNBN & TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN were insignificant but positive & negative impact on inflation to Nigeria. Whereas, a unit increase in MSSNBN, INT, BUDGETDEFICITNBN & TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN increases inflation to Nigeria by 0.004%, 1.621%, 0.004% & 0.002% respectively. Also, a unit increase in GDPNBN, IMPNBN, EXR &

DOMESICDEBTNBN decreases inflation to Nigeria by 0.001%, 0.000%, 0.128% & 0.001%. The error correction term CointEq(-1) is well behaved as its coefficient is negative and significant. The coefficient of the ECT of -1.09 reveals that the speed with which inflation to Nigeria adjusts the regressors is about 109% in the short run. The R- square value of 0.76 shows that about 76% variations of the inflation to Nigeria are jointly explained by variations in the explanatory variables of the model. The probability F – statistic value of 0.000026 shows that the overall model is significant in explaining the impact of money supply on inflation in Nigeria. The short run and long run result of all the variables in the model is well behaved as they conform to a prior expectation. The results of the diagnostic test of the model adequacy for the model are presented in Table 5 and figure 10.

Table 5. Summary of Diagnostic Tests for the Model

Model 1			
Breusch – Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	2.771240	Prob. F	0.0826
Obs*R-squared	7.316810	Prob. Chi-Square	0.0258
Correlogram Squared Residuals Probability Value	0.777		
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.458713	Prob. F	0.9210
Obs*R-squared	6.814183	Prob. Chi-Square	0.8696
Jarque – Bera Test of Normality			
Jarque – Bera	24.08657	Probability	0.000006

Source: The Author’s Computation 2023.

Note: Tests critical values are computed at 5% level of significance.

Figure 10. Result of CUSUM and CUSUM of squares Test of Stability for the Model

The outcome of the diagnostic tests of the model adequacy is satisfactory as the assumptions of normality, homoscedasticity and no auto – correlation is not violated. This is evidenced by the probability value of all test statistics which is greater than 0.05. The cusum

and cusum of squares tests of stability results show that estimated parameter coefficients are stable at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the model is well specified, and hence the result is plausible.

Table 6. Granger-causality test Results

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
MSNBN does not Granger Cause INF	39	1.08044	0.3508
INF does not Granger Cause MSNBN		0.61418	0.5470
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause INF	39	1.45906	0.2466
INF does not Granger Cause GDPNBN		0.08979	0.9143
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause INF	39	0.93502	0.4024
INF does not Granger Cause IMPNBN		0.05137	0.9500
EXR does not Granger Cause INF	39	1.43623	0.2519
INF does not Granger Cause EXR		0.58557	0.5623
INT does not Granger Cause INF	39	9.54109	0.0005
INF does not Granger Cause INT		3.83099	0.0316
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause INF	39	0.38437	0.6838
INF does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN		0.27901	0.7582
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause INF	39	0.73546	0.4868
INF does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		0.16411	0.8493
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause INF	39	0.93120	0.4039
INF does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		0.07767	0.9254
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	16.8826	8.E-06
MSNBN does not Granger Cause GDPNBN		1.57089	0.2226
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	4.98254	0.0127
MSNBN does not Granger Cause IMPNBN		6.77425	0.0033
EXR does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	2.21383	0.1248
MSNBN does not Granger Cause EXR		2.66843	0.0839
INT does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	1.87908	0.1683
MSNBN does not Granger Cause INT		0.77661	0.4680
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	0.59124	0.5592
MSNBN does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN		4.87413	0.0138
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	1.11210	0.3405
MSNBN does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		14.7289	2.E-05
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause MSNBN	39	0.25937	0.7730
MSNBN does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		2.86127	0.0710
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause GDPNBN	39	4.32086	0.0213
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause IMPNBN		11.1112	0.0002
EXR does not Granger Cause GDPNBN	39	9.69337	0.0005
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause EXR		4.76793	0.0150
INT does not Granger Cause GDPNBN	39	0.55525	0.5790
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause INT		1.18693	0.3175
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause GDPNBN	39	0.92891	0.4048
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN		4.14650	0.0245
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause GDPNBN	39	0.55021	0.5819
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		16.1849	1.E-05
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause GDPNBN	39	1.03544	0.3660
GDPNBN does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		5.48229	0.0086
EXR does not Granger Cause IMPNBN	39	6.71349	0.0035
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause EXR		3.58402	0.0387

INT does not Granger Cause IMPNBN	39	0.27579	0.7607
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause INT		0.78530	0.4641
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause IMPNBN	39	5.23348	0.0104
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN		2.24580	0.1213
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause IMPNBN	39	5.84839	0.0066
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		9.86101	0.0004
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause IMPNBN	39	3.26163	0.0506
IMPNBN does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		2.89455	0.0690
INT does not Granger Cause EXR	39	0.34825	0.7084
EXR does not Granger Cause INT		1.01703	0.3724
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause EXR	39	2.60444	0.0886
EXR does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN		1.14836	0.3292
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause EXR	39	2.78349	0.0759
EXR does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		0.01721	0.9830
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause EXR	39	1.69073	0.1995
EXR does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		0.60975	0.5493
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause INT	39	0.28697	0.7523
INT does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN		0.02744	0.9730
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause INT	39	0.49331	0.6149
INT does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		0.31558	0.7315
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause INT	39	0.69131	0.5078
INT does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		0.13697	0.8725
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN	39	5.32253	0.0097
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN		1.59545	0.2176
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause BUDGETDEFICITNBN	39	2.02972	0.1470
BUDGETDEFICITNBN does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		5.71776	0.0072
TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause DOMESICDEBTNBN	39	0.23304	0.7934
DOMESICDEBTNBN does not Granger Cause TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN		1.86171	0.1709

Source: The Author's Computation 2023.

Table 6 contains the results of Granger Causality tests. The essence of this test is to establish a causal relationship among Inflation (INF), Money Supply (MS), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Import (IMP), Exchange Rate (EXR), Interest (INT), Budget Deficit (BD), Domestic Debt (DD) and Total Government Debt (TGD). This test gives us the direction of causality among these variables. There are usually two outcomes of this test, unidirectional or bidirectional relationship. In this study, it was observed that there was a bidirectional relationship among the variables as well unidirectional relationship existed, that is, INT causes INF, INF causes INT, GDP causes MS, IMP causes MS, MS causes IMP, MS causes BUDGETDEFICIT, MS causes DOMESICDEBT, IMP causes GDP, GDP causes IMP, EXR causes GDP, GDP causes EXR GDP causes BUDGETDEFICITNBN, GDP causes DOMESICDEBT, GDP causes TOTALGOVTDEBTNBN, EXR causes IMP,

IMP Causes EXR, BUDGETDEFICITNBN Causes IMP, DOMESICDEBT causes IMP, IMP causes DOMESICDEBT, TOTALGOVTDEBT causes IMP, DOMESICDEBT causes BUDGETDEFICIT and BUDGETDEFICIT causes TOTALGOVTDEBT.

Conclusion, Recommendations and Policy Implication

Empirical evidence from the paper has shown that there is a positive and negative significant relationship between Inflation and Interest towards money supply on inflation in Nigeria. This means, there is an increase in Inflation and Interest, the rate of inflation is a diversely affected by fuelling inflation in line with the empirical finding of the research work. Hence, to reduce the level of inflation and ensure price stability in Nigeria, the monetary authority needs to regulate the amount of money supply into the

Nigerian economy. Therefore, should government intensify the effort to combat inflation by encouraging the monetary authority to put in place policies measures that are gear toward reducing the amount of money in circulation?

Depending on the results of the study, some recommendations can be identified, including:

(A). The study finds a significant positive relationship between Inflation and Interest; it shows that continued the policies put in place by the monetary and fiscal authorities in Nigeria should be such that will encourage the supply of money to a certain level in order to curb inflation in Nigeria in the short medium and long term.

(B). However, the study finds a significant positive and negative relationship between Inflation and Interest. As a result, restrictive monetary policies should be put in place by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to ensure that inflationary pressure is pulled down to a reasonable level as money supply is one of the factors causing price instability in Nigeria.

As for the policy implication, having seen that there exist a long run relationship between Inflation and explanatory variables (Money Supply, Gross Domestic Product, Import, Exchange Rate, Interest, Budget Deficit, Domestic Debt and Total Government Debt) through the use of co-integration test, It implies that government should reduce her outrageous expenditures and control the incessant budget deficit that has been recorded in Nigeria while the central bank should desist from creating cheap currency so as to curb excess supply of money in the economy. In addition, the government should diversify the economy; enact easy export policy, subsidise fuel price since they turn out to be one the factors that triggers high inflation in Nigeria possibly because of the ripple effect they exhibit on economic activities in form of high transportation, high prices of food, necessity items to mention a few. Therefore, the study suggests more focus on other factors that trigger inflation in the country other than money supply so as to reduce its menace on the economic well-being.

References

- Anyanwu J.C., (1993). *Monetary Economics: Theory, policy and Institutions*, Onitsha. Joance Educational Publishing Ltd.
- Alexander, A.A., Andow, A., & Danpome, M.G. (2015). Analysis of the main determinants of inflation in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(2), 144-155.
- Almahdi, M.A.M., & Faroug, M.K.Y. (2018). Modelling the determinants of inflation in Sudan using a generalized method of moments for the period 2000 – 2017. *International Journal of Information Research and Review*, 05(02), 5154-5165.
- AlNaif, K., Shahtite, M., & AlTaib, S. (2018). The relationship between money supply and inflation in the Jordanian Economy. *IUG Journal of Economics and Business*, 26(1), 64.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (1998). Statistical Bulletin. Vol. 5. No.11.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (2011). What is Monetary Policy? *Understanding Monetary Policy Series*. Series, 1, 1- 45.
- Dhungel, K.R. (2014) Estimation of Short and Long Run Equilibrium Coefficients in Error Correction Model: Empirical Evidence from Nepal. *International Journal of Econometrics and Financial Management*, 2(6), 214-219. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ijefm-2-6-1>
- Danlami, I.A., Mohamad, H.H. & Hassan, S. (2020). Money supply and inflation in Nigeria: The myth of the monetarist theory of inflation. *Journal of Economics and Sustainability*, 2, 1-13.
- Greenidge, K. & DaCosta, D. (2009). Determinants of Inflation in Selected Caribbean Countries. *Business, Finance and Economics in Emerging Economies*, 4(2), 272-297.
- Gujarati, D. N. (2009). *Basic econometrics*. New York, Boston: McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Hicham, A. (2020). Money Supply, Inflation and Economic Growth: Co-Integration and Causality Analysis. *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai Oeconomica*, 65(2), 29–45. <https://doi.org/10.2478/SUBBOEC-2020-0008>

- Islam, R., Ghani, A., Mahyudin, E., & Manickam, N. (2017). Determinants of Factors that Affecting Inflation in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(2), 355–364.
- Jhinga, M. L. (2002). *Macroeconomic Theory*. Low Itrvrinde, Publication Ltd New Delhi.
- Kiganda, E.O. (2014). Effect of Macroeconomic Factors on Commercial Banks Profitability in Kenya: Case of Equity Bank Limited. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(2), 46-56.
- Mankiw, N. G. (2011). *Principles of Economics, 5th edition*. South-Western Cengage Learning.
- Nwachukwu, P., Dibie, A. C., & Ogudo, P. (2014). Effectiveness of Monetary Policy in Reducing Inflation in Nigeria (1970-2013). Retrieved from <https://portal.bazeuniversity.edu.ng/student/assets/thesis/20201208223422545811382.pdf>
- Onwioduokit E.A. (2002) Fiscal Deficit and Inflation in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation of Casual Relationships. *CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 37(2), 1-1.
- Okere, E. J., & Sanni, T. A. (2005). *Money and the Nigerian Financial System*. Owerri: Jeso International Publication.
- Ogbokor, C.A., & Sunde, T. (2011). Is Namibia's inflation import driven? An econometric investigation. *Journal of Development Alternative and Area Studies*, 30(1, 2), 1-14.
- Olorunfemi, S., & Adeleke, P. (2013). Money Supply and Inflation in Nigeria: Implications for National Development. *Modern Economy*, 4(3), 161-170. <https://doi.org/10.4236/me.2013.43018>
- Obi, O.K. & Uzodigwe, A. A. (2015). Dynamic Impact of Money Supply on Inflation: Evidence from ECOWAS Member States. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, 6(3) 10-17. <https://doi.org/10.9790/5933-06331017>
- Otto, G., and Ukpere, W. I. (2016). Inflation in Nigeria: Possible determinants and remedies to tackle it in Nigeria. *Risk Governance & Control: Financial Markets & Institutions*, 6(2), 35-43. <https://doi.org/10.22495/rcgv6i2art5>
- Ofori-Frimpon, K., Ofori, C. F., Danquah, B. A., & Zhang, X. (2017). The impact of money supply on inflation, a case of Ghana. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 3(1), 3212-2318.
- Oumbe, T.H. (2018). Monetary Policy and Inflation: Empirical Evidence from Cameroon. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(5), 200-207. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijefm.20180605.11>
- Okotori, T. (2020). The Dynamics of monetary policy and inflation in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, 10(2), 37-49. <https://doi.org/10.9790/5933-1002013749>
- Pesaran, M.H., Shin, Y & Smith, R.J. (2001) Bounds Testing Approaches to the Analysis of Level Relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16, 289 -326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>
- Roffia, B. & Zaghini, A. (2008), Excess Money Growth and Inflation Dynamics. Bank of Italy Temi di Discussione (Working Paper) No. 657.
- Ryckowski, M. (2021). Money and inflation in inflation-targeting regimes – new evidence from time–frequency analysis. *Journal of Applied Economics*, 24(1), 17–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15140326.2020.1830461>
- Sultana, N., Koli, R., & Firoj, M. (2019). Causal relationship of money supply and inflation: A study of Bangladesh. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 9(1), 42-50. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.aefr.2019.91.42.51>
- Tang, C.F. & Lean, H.H. (2007) Is Inflation always a monetary phenomenon in Malaysia? New empirical Evidence. *Malaysian Journal of Economic Studies*, 44(2), 95-105.
- Undji, V.J., & Kaulihowa, T. (2015). Determinants of inflation in Namibia: A cointegration approach. *Journal of Business Management Dynamics*, 5(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jbmd.v5i1.12>

Appendix 1

Table 1. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	INF	MSS	GDP	IMP	EXR	INT	BD	DD	TGD
	(%)	(N' Billion)	(N' Billion)	(N' Billion)		(%)	(N' Billion)	(N' Billion)	(N' Billion)
Mean	18.85220	8126.415	37550.91	4646005.0	108.1675	11.56526	-923.1877	3594.826	5906.811
Median	12.88000	1269.322	8234.494	1358180.0	111.9433	9.980000	-117.2371	1016.974	2843.561
Maximum	72.84000	40318.29	176075.5	22394498	399.9636	23.99000	32.04940	19242.56	35097.79
Minimum	5.390000	14.47117	139.3105	5983.600	0.610025	4.704871	-7118.708	11.19260	13.52380
Std. Deviation	16.68089	11875.70	50434.86	6244170.0	109.9115	4.807634	1734.778	5162.039	8298.340
Skewness	1.863065	1.362983	1.284324	1.431646	0.972937	1.045660	-2.304480	1.536557	1.986693
Kurtosis	5.322050	3.560473	3.459285	4.161221	3.172454	3.453622	7.466158	4.246979	6.386153
Jarque-Bera	32.92977	13.23107	11.63186	16.30924	6.519282	7.823131	70.36467	18.78994	46.55861
Probability	0.000000	0.001339	0.002980	0.000287	0.038402	0.020009	0.000000	0.000083	0.000000
Sum	772.9400	333183.0	1539587	1.90E+08	4434.867	474.1756	-37850.69	147387.9	242179.3
Sum Sq. Dev.	11130.08	5.64E+09	1.02E+11	1.56E+15	483221.4	924.5336	1.20E+08	1.07E+09	2.75E+09
Observations	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

Source: The Author's Computation 2023